

Low-voltage DC-DC converter for IoT and on-chip energy harvester applications

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Abstract: The power saving issue as well as clean energy harvesting for wireless and cost-affordable electronics (e.g. IoT applications, sensor nodes or medical implants), belong to very attractive research topics recently. With this in mind, the paper addresses one of the most important parts of the energy conversion system chain – the power management unit. The core of such a unit will be formed by an inductor-less, low-voltage DC-DC converter based on the cross-coupled dynamic-threshold charge pump topology. The charge pump utilizes a power-efficient ON/OFF regulation feedback loop, especially designed for strict low-voltage start-up conditions by a driver booster. Together, they serve as the masters to control the charge pump output (up to 600 mV), depending on the voltage value produced by a renewable energy source available in the environment. Low-power feature is also ensured by a careful design of the hysteresis-based bulk-driven comparator and fully integrated switched-capacitor voltage divider, omitting the static power consumption. The presented converter could also employ the on-chip RF-based energy harvester for use in a wireless power transfer system.

Keywords: DC-DC converter, charge pump, energy harvesting, low-voltage, IoT, wireless power transfer system.

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1. Introduction and motivation

Recent advances in design and fabrication of integrated circuits (ICs) opened a space for development of wireless, miniature and powerful sensor nodes, as well as wearable and biomedical devices. Since the device’s case size is constrained to a few cm^3 , standard IC power supplying using a battery is rather limited. This constrain forces the development of new IC design and power management methods for low-voltage and low-power conditions. These approaches include the following:

- Energy harvesting using power tracking algorithms,
- Low-voltage circuit topologies,
- Voltage converters with low start-up voltage,
- Low-voltage driving circuits.

Energy harvesters (EHs) are based on converting an alternative energy source to electrical energy [1]. Among others, photovoltaic, thermoelectric [2], piezoelectric [3,4], acoustic [5], triboelectric [6] or electromagnetic generators [7,8] are widely used for this purpose. Supplying the IC using an appropriate EH allows the whole device becoming energetically autonomous. On the other hand, considering a small build volume, the EH output voltage value and also power are insufficient to continuously supply an integrated circuit. As overall EH methodology became promising, solutions for the above mentioned issue have emerged.

35 The radio-frequency energy as a potential power source reaches relatively low
36 power density compared to solar and piezoelectric energy [9]. On the other hand, it
37 is more stable due to source regularity and lower weather dependency. Taking these
38 attributes into account, the radio-frequency energy harvesting (RF-EH) is widely adopted
39 for ultra-low power IC and their application. The RF-EH achieves high reliability and
40 small form factor of a transducer. According to the state of the art, the RF-EH systems
41 dominantly employ inductive DC-DC converters. These are more attractive over the
42 capacitive counterparts (charge pumps), due to higher power conversion efficiency
43 (PCE) and suitability for low-voltage start-up [10]. Recent research revealed that the
44 charge pump-based step-up converters reach improved PCE and start-up ability [11,12].
45 However, the research across utilization of charge pumps (CPs) in energy harvesting
46 systems is relatively unexplored [13,14]. This inspires further research towards great
47 examination of CPs as an alternative to inductive step-up converters for ultra-low voltage
48 EH systems.

49 As the output impedance of an EH system is rather high, it is essential to match
50 the following IC input impedance in order to preserve the EH source capability. The
51 more sophisticated approach is the use of the maximum power point tracking (MPPT)
52 algorithms [15]. MPPT dynamically adjusts the EH load impedance according to its
53 power curve, allowing higher power extraction. In order to achieve sufficiently high
54 value of supply voltage for IC using EHs, the switched regulators are used to carry
55 out the conversion of voltage from lower to higher values. One of the widely used
56 regulator topologies suitable for full integration on chip are a CPs. Its operation is based
57 on a charge being accumulated in capacitors and sequentially propagated to the output
58 through switches. As the charge pump itself must be designed for ultra-low voltage
59 conditions, while being supplied from an EH, the proper operation of switches becomes
60 a challenge. For the charge accumulation, CPs utilize rather large capacitors. Such
61 capacitors require adequate drivers, which are well suited with an inverter. To maintain
62 sufficient propagation delay in the capacitor charging, which limits the overall operation,
63 it is crucial to open and close the inverter transistors as much as possible. This otherwise
64 trivial requirement becomes a challenge in the environment of supply voltage under
65 200 mV. The clock signals (CLKs) therefore require a dedicated boosting circuit with
66 adequate driving capability, increasing the value of CLK signal [16]. As any voltage
67 conversion technique has its limits from effectivity point of view, it is essential to design
68 ICs using low-voltage and low-power approach. In the field of analog IC design, such
69 methods include the g_m/I_D design methodology and so-called bulk-driven approach.
70 Such methods of IC design for ultra low-voltage applications form the core of research
71 presented in this paper, where bulk-driven design approach has been implemented in
72 design of several subcircuits (e.g. a charge pump core, a boosted driver, comparator
73 and a voltage divider) to improve the total EH performance focused on low-voltage
74 conditions.

75 From the state of the art development point of view, the most important attributes
76 of the developed EH power management unit (EH-PMU) based on the proposed DC-DC
77 converter are the following:

- 78 • Minimum start-up voltage of CP,
- 79 • Output-to-input voltage ratio,
- 80 • Output voltage ripple,
- 81 • Self-stainability,
- 82 • Power throughput,
- 83 • Overall EH-PMU effectivity in the target power range.

84 The last three attributes represent the primary objectives for our research, where
85 the self-stainability and the overall EH-PMU effectivity are ensured by low-power
86 requirements originated from analog-less design, and the power throughput is achieved
87 by the modified structure of the CP core using a dedicated driver and taking into
88 account reliable switching and the associated frequency/timing requirements. The

89 CP-based PMU functionality has been verified by experimental measurements and then,
 90 successfully implemented into RF-EH systems. Moreover, the valuable experimental
 91 results from the bulk-driven design represent a part of novelty in terms of application of
 92 unconventional design approaches in low-voltage systems.

93 The paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, the developed DC-DC converter and
 94 its main building blocks are described. Section 3 presents the application of the converter
 95 in an RF-based energy harvesting system. Evaluation results obtained by measurement
 96 of the experimental chip prototypes are presented in Section 4, where simulated and
 97 measured results are compared as well. Comparison of the results achieved in this
 98 research with other works is addressed in Section 5, where also a short discussion and
 99 conclusions can be found.

100 2. DC-DC Converter System

101 In order to address the issues and trends described in the previous section, a
 102 regulated low-voltage (subthreshold), step-up DC-DC converter based on switching
 103 capacitors, also known as a charge pump, has been proposed. Fig. 1 shows the top level
 104 block diagram of the developed system with highlighted parts that were integrated on
 105 a chip. The CP-based converter consists of the following parts: a CP Core as the main
 106 part of the voltage stepping and conversion, then an integrated voltage divider realized
 107 by switching capacitors (marked as type 1), clock boosters driving digital logic blocks
 108 with potentially mismatched supply voltages, a low-voltage comparator, a CP driver
 109 and a frequency divider with fixed dead time. The proper connection of these parts into
 110 a feedback configuration can control the output voltage V_{CP_OUT} to the desired regulated
 111 value according custom specifications. The ON/OFF based regulation feedback loop
 112 approach is implemented to manage this task.

Figure 1. Top level of the proposed CP-based DC-DC converter.

113 2.1. Charge Pump Core

114 The most important part of the proposed converter is the CP Core (Fig. 2). This block
 115 consists of 9 cells organized into series-parallel configuration creating unreconfigurable
 116 structure with 3 parallel branches (multi-branch structure at higher system level). Each
 117 branch consists of three CP cells connected into a cascade. In the ideal case, cascading
 118 cells allows to boost the CP Core input voltage V_{OUT_DC} up to $V_{OUT_DC} + NV_{OUT_DC}$, where
 119 N is the number of cascaded stages. This can be achieved if supplying the CP core
 120 as well as the driver by the same voltage value. However, non-ideal CPs have many
 121 parasitics that deteriorate the performance such as the finite output impedance including

122 modulation index, parasitic capacities at switching nodes, etc. [17–19]. Under low-
 123 voltage subthreshold conditions and the high current throughput requirement (see
 124 RF-harvester application in Section 3) across the system, the output impedance plays
 125 a very important role and should be minimized as much as possible. In this sense, we
 126 would like to state the following:

- 127 (a) *impedance modulation index*, which is the result of finite on-state transistor resis-
 128 tance $R_{T,ON}$ of main switches - M_{N1-2} and M_{P1-2} (see Fig. 2), is usually reduced
 129 by bootstrapping techniques implemented in the CP cell [20,21],
 130 (b) the ideal term $\propto N_C/kF_{SW}C_{FLY}$, which is valid for linear CP, is topology-dependent
 131 and can be managed exclusively by topology interventions. N_C is a number of
 132 stages in the cascade, k is a number of power flow patches known as branches,
 133 F_{SW} is clock frequency, C_{FLY} represents the main flying capacitor (in Fig. 2 de-
 134 noted as C_{1x-Nx} where x stands for p or n) [18].

135 To deal with statement (a), the Dynamic Threshold Cross-Coupled Charge Pump
 136 (DT-CCCP) has been chosen as a good candidate. Generally, the CCCP has promising po-
 137 tential under low-voltage conditions without applying any special "external" techniques,
 138 since the bootstrapping intrinsically includes such a feature. Despite of a few inherited
 139 drawbacks, the positives outweigh negatives in a broader perception [22–24]. Moreover,
 140 the recent research proves that if dynamic- V_{TH} technique is employed to minimize the
 141 impedance modulation index, together with careful design based on parasitic aware
 142 approach, the current throughput and power efficiency can be very optimistic even in the
 143 case of the full on-chip implementation [17]. On the other hand, in relation to statement
 144 (b), the CP topology intervention is required. Taking into account the current throughput
 145 requirement, the linear dual-branch CP has been selected because it is characterized by
 146 lower sensitivity of voltage conversion to the presence of parasitic capacitances (under
 147 the same capacitor requirements in the total value) compare to the non-linear CPs (as
 148 Fibonacci or exponential ones). For this reason, linear CPs are more suitable for heavy
 149 loads since a lower number of stages is needed for the same conversion ratio, and hence
 150 the lower output impedance [19]. Additionally, the branch parallelization (equivalent
 151 to multi-branch approach at CP cell level) at higher system levels has been used to
 152 redistribute the current and decrease the output impedance in both terms (a) and (b)
 153 (the value of the individual capacitors was retained).

Figure 2. Multi-stage CP Core block (detail view of the DT-CCCP cell).

154 Transformation of a single branch into multiple ones withdrew the need for on-
 155 state resistance $R_{T,ON}$ of the main switches M_{N1-2} and M_{P1-2} but brings more strict

156 requirements for the driver, which charges flying capacitors C_{1x-Nx} and shifts-up the
 157 voltage at their terminals. Because the system is synchronized into two clock phases, the
 158 driver's inverter must sustain currents flowing through all capacitors during individual
 159 phases without any drastic impact on the impedance modulation index. It is important
 160 to note that if the system can be investigated through a representative cell [17], such a
 161 modification does not affect the $(RC)_{cell}$ constant of the charging/discharging cell itself
 162 if the values of transistor and capacitor are preserved. However, if a driver is non-ideal,
 163 i.e on-state resistance $R_{D,ON}$ has a finite value, the original $R_{T,ON}C_{TOT}$ is increased about
 164 $NR_{D,ON}C_{TOT}$, where C_{TOT} represents the total capacitance seen at the internal center
 165 node of the CP cell, and N is the total number of CP stages.

166 2.2. Boosted Driver

167 Consequently, the proposed CP consists of a stand-alone boosted driver circuit to
 168 solve the above-mentioned issue as an alternative to other competitive techniques with
 169 different primary purposes in relation to ultra-low voltage research area (e.g. a clock
 170 booster based driver, topology reconfiguration approach, implementation of adiabatic
 171 principle, and many others [10,24,25]). The transistor level schematic of the proposed
 172 driver and detailed cross-connection with a complementary replica circuit are shown
 173 in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4, respectively. The implemented driver originates from already
 174 characterized version (presented in [26,27]), which was extended by another auxiliary
 175 circuit to further improve the performance of the boosted output inverter. The previous
 176 version just boosts the gate of high-side part of the inverter formed by PMOS transistor
 177 M_{P1} to the negative voltage of $-2V_{SUPP}$. The low-side part was of our interest and
 178 therefore, kept untouched. Despite this implementation, the driver has been successfully
 179 implemented into a chip prototype of regulated DC-DC converter, and is capable to
 180 drive more than 100 pF capacitor with a few units of ns propagation delay under the
 181 supply voltage value of 200 mV and the clock frequency of 1 MHz [26].

Figure 3. The driver scheme using bulk-driven cross-connection cores.

182 In the converter design, the CP Core has been modified including a larger number of
 183 stages. For this reason, also the driver had to be adapted to that and the improved version
 184 also takes care about the low-side part of the inverter formed by the NMOS transistor
 185 M_{N1} across the boosted gate voltage of $2V_{SUPP}$ in the ideal case. The operation principle
 186 can be closely examined from Fig. 4, where the transistors and capacitors are organized
 187 to enable a serial-parallel reconfiguration for doubling the voltage value. In Fig. 4, the
 188 states of individual transistor switches in both clock phases are highlighted, where green
 189 and red represents on-state and off-state, respectively. The blue arrows show the energy
 190 flow of charging/discharging process. It should be noted that the presence of positive
 191 voltage higher than the supply value, derived for the input voltage $V_{OUT,DC}$ in our case,

192 is not only used for driving the main switch M_{N1} but also controls auxiliary NMOS
 193 switches. Including all logic gates, the dynamic- V_{TH} technique has been also employed
 194 for some critical transistors in the driver, and for this reason, natural trade-off between
 195 the maximum supply voltage, switching frequency, and capacitor/transistor sizes exists.
 196 For instance, the node CLK_{OUT} is relatively sensitive to this trade-off, because in time of
 197 driving transistor M_{N2} to the voltage of $2V_{SUPP}$, M_{N2} transistor has negative potential
 198 of about $-V_{SUPP}$ at its source terminal and the bulk diode can be activated to discharge
 199 C_{B3} and charge C_{B2} (both effects have negative impact on the driver performance). As a
 200 consequence, if $2V_{SUPP}$ represents too high value and frequency is too low, the driver
 201 can be the most critical loss contributor, and this is manifested in squeezing the efficiency
 202 for the higher input voltage compared to the lower one (in relation to the lower and
 203 upper switching frequency). Based on the simulation, to ensure a reliable functionality
 204 under the nominal conditions across all technology corners and the temperature range
 205 ($-20^{\circ}\text{C} - 85^{\circ}\text{C}$), the size of capacitors C_{B1} and C_{B2} should be doubled ($15\text{ pF} \Rightarrow 30\text{ pF}$)
 206 compared to the previous version, and the value of the additional capacitor C_{B3} has to
 207 set to 40 pF . It should be also noted that the performance of the proposed driver has not
 208 been explicitly investigated but was implicitly carried out only as part of the system to
 209 which this work is primarily dedicated.

Figure 4. Driver operation principle. (a) $DRIVER_{IN} = \text{Log } 0$. (b) $DRIVER_{IN} = \text{Log } 1$.

210 The inputs to the driver cores are generated by a simple logic acting as gated
 211 clock generator controlled by a comparator with hysteresis across a feedback loop. The
 212 frequency of clocks, i.e. $CLK_{CB,LF}$ and complementary twin $nCLK_{CB,LF}$, are managed
 213 by an external CLK_{EXT} signal with a half of the clock frequency (see Fig. 1). In other
 214 words, the frequency divider with a non-overlapping clock generator are implemented
 215 through standard T flip-flop topology followed by NAND-based dead-time circuit (with
 216 delay gates in feedback path defined). Since the entire driver and frequency divider
 217 are supplied by the same voltage $V_{OUT,DC}$ during the experiment, using a clock booster
 218 or a level shifter in low-frequency branch is out of relevance. Therefore, an optional
 219 one (bounded by dashed gray-box in Fig. 1) has been designed on a chip but omitted
 220 in measurements. We have to make it clear that in Section 4, the frequency range of
 221 $5 - 200\text{ kHz}$ representing the external clocks and clocks for switching the driver has to
 222 be considered half smaller.

223 2.3. Voltage Divider Branch

224 The high-frequency branches are directly fed from the external clocks and drive
 225 transmission gates (TGs) in the capacitor-switching voltage divider across fast drivers
 226 and inverters (designed as *type 1* in top-level block scheme, Fig. 1). The main objective

227 of this step is to eliminate static power consumption and exploit a greater inherited
 228 compactness compared to bulky resistors with higher resistance value. The proposed
 229 voltage divider of *type 1* is shown in Fig. 5a, where capacitors can be arranged by
 230 TGs connected into a serial-parallel cycling reconfiguration. Because capacitors C_{VD1}
 231 and C_{VD2} are of the same size (capacitance of 15 pF), the ratio of ≈ 0.5 is provided at
 232 steady state. However, if a dynamic- V_{TH} technique is employed together with quite
 233 large TGs ensuring reliable on-state under low-voltage conditions ($C_{P_{OUT}} \approx 400$ mV,
 234 $V_{TH} = 250 - 300$ mV/300 - 350 mV for long/short channel, respectively in a standard
 235 130 nm CMOS technology), the dominant parasitic effects as charge injection and clock
 236 feedthrough cannot be fully neglected. Additionally, the dynamic bulk-switching fosters
 237 discharging effect that degenerates the deviding ratio - the issues of low frequency.
 238 Mainly for these phenomena, the post-extract simulation (PEX) under the nominal condi-
 239 tion reveals 92 - 224 mV of DIV_{CAP} variation in DC value, where for 25 kHz and 50 kHz
 240 driving frequencies, the best results of 193.4 mV and 210.3 mV are achieved, respectively.
 241 Fig. 5b shows the conversion gain transfer function of $C_{P_{OUT}}$ to DIV_{CAP} node through
 242 zero harmonic getting from PSS-PAC type analysis. The achieved results demonstrate
 243 slightly lower ratio around -7.4 dB in comparison to the intended value of -6 dB. With a
 244 link to time-based analysis observations, the non-negligible influence of parasitics effects
 245 can be deduced. Adding the filtrating capacitor C_{VD3} with the capacitance value of
 246 40 pF at the output node, the capacitor-switching voltage divider is getting character of
 247 1-st order low-pass filter with frequency-dependent corner frequency of 1 kHz - 20 kHz
 248 range related to clocks $CLK_{CB, HF}$ and $nCLK_{CB, HF}$, which is the characteristic property of
 249 many other systems utilizing the switching capacitor technique. Because the divider and
 250 control logic are necessarily supplied by the high-voltage domain (i.e. $V_{C_{P_{OUT}}}$), the use of
 251 clock booster or level shifter auxiliary circuits must be also a part of the design. In other
 252 words, the low-voltage domain (supplied by the input voltage $V_{OUT_{DC}}$) must be able to
 253 control the high-voltage domain and ensure its reliable operation. For this purpose, the
 254 popular Nakagome's clock booster with dynamic- V_{TH} technique was employed [20,28].

Figure 5. Switched-capacitor voltage divider 1 to 0.5. (a) Circuit implementation. (b) PEX simulation of conversion gain function under $V_{C_{P_{OUT}}} = 400$ mV and typical 23°C conditions. Clocks and digital blocks are supplied by the same voltage.

255 To create a complete picture about the developed CP system, it should be also noted
 256 that based on the observations described above, an alternative solution in the form of a
 257 common resistor-based voltage divider (marked as *type 2* in Fig. 1) has been investigated
 258 and a comparison is carried out in Section 4.1. In this case, the voltage divider has been
 259 realized externally (off-chip) and connected through DIV_{EXT} node. Thus, the supply
 260 voltage of the switched-capacitor voltage divider has been grounded and the fuse burnt
 261 out.

2.4. Comparator with Hysteresis

The divided voltage V_{DIVCAP} is then compared to the reference voltage $V_{REFCOMP}$ generated externally, and a suitable control signal at node $CTRLDRIVER$ is produced (see Fig. 1). The decision block providing this task is a rail-to-rail voltage comparator depicted in Fig. 6, which has been designed for the power supply voltage of 400 mV with emphasis on the robustness and low value of the input offset without the need of post-processing trimming [29,30]. The topology is capable of working with even lower supply voltages thanks to two stacked transistors. The proposed comparator works in so-called current regime. The input transistors act as current sources modulated by the input voltage applied to their bulk terminals. The current generated in the input branches is then mirrored in order to create the differential voltage in nodes $diff$ and \overline{diff} , which is processed by a digital block. The proposed comparator topology also contains built-in programmable hysteresis controlled by 2-bit input signal. The hysteresis does not require any external components and its level and symmetry can be full-custom designed by W/L ratio of the respective transistors. The enable function shuts-off the current sources, sets the output to a defined logic state, and reduces the power consumption into a leakage level. For this purpose, the *Log 0* level has been selected to allow passing the clock signals into the driver, which in this application, ensure a reliable start also at a poorly low defined supply voltage. The selected measured characteristics are displayed in Fig. 6b, where the measured current draw includes the consumption of several ESD structures, IC package, PCB and probes parasitics. This means that for on-chip application, the power consumption can be considered near or even down to 1 μW under typical conditions that can be supported by the further reduction of the supply voltage.

Figure 6. Implemented bulk-driven rail-to-rail comparator (redrawn from [30]). (a) Transistor level diagram. (b) Current consumption for various reference voltages.

3. Application

To demonstrate the suitability of the developed DC-DC converter in the application example – as a PMU in an RF-based energy harvesting system (RF-EH), we demonstrated its functionality in conjunction with a fully integrated wireless power transfer (WPT) receiver system. Thus, this section gives a brief description of the implemented fully integrated rectenna (rectifying antenna) based solution used for experimental validation. Due to fabrication related limitations, mainly the maximum allowable area of the on-chip antenna (OCA), a very low overall coupling coefficient is expected, resulting in limited output power. Therefore, the internal components of the WPT system were optimized for low-voltage and low-power operation. Such a WPT system is used as a power source for the DC-DC converter, and therefore, is connected to the converter input (the Energy Harvester block in Fig. 1). A more detailed description of the implemented WPT system can be found in [31].

299 3.1. WPT system description

300 A fully integrated WPT system can be divided into three main parts: the OCA, an
 301 impedance matching network and the rectifier circuit, as shown in Fig. 8. The main
 302 consideration for the design of the later two parts are parameters of the OCA itself, as
 303 the antenna determines the usable frequency band as well as available power of the
 304 system as a whole.

305 The implemented OCA was optimized for the limited available chip area on the
 306 manufactured prototype. To compensate this major limitation, a layer-modified version
 307 of the recently proposed structure (described in [32]) was used. The designed OCA
 308 structure is shown in Fig. 7, where the topology is based on a symmetrical multi-layer
 309 stacked inductor, suitable for use in a standard CMOS technology. In comparison to more
 310 commonly utilized designs, based on simple spiral coils, this proprietary structure offers
 311 improved inductance as well as quality factor values, both very important parameters
 312 for the overall WPT system performance. Such an inductor design achieves best overall
 313 performance at frequencies around $200\text{ MHz} \pm 10\%$, with the previously measured
 314 example exhibiting the maximum quality factor in this region.

Figure 7. Designed OCA of the implemented EH (turn details: width = $60\ \mu\text{m}$, space = $12.5\ \mu\text{m}$, realized using top 6 layers). (a) 2D structure. (b) 3D structure.

315 The impedance matching network and the main rectifier circuit of the proposed
 316 WPT system were designed to best utilize the above-described inductor design, taking
 317 into account the expected values of quality factor and inductance of the OCA. The
 318 impedance matching network was designed for the maximum power transfer, as the
 319 expected harvested values are very low due to the chip area restrictions. By utilizing
 320 a capacitor-only structure, we avoided possible interactions between multiple on-chip
 321 coils. The implemented structure consists of a tunable parallel capacitor, used to form
 322 a resonant circuit with the EH coil and thus raise the harvested voltage, and a series
 323 capacitance formed by the rectifier structure itself [33]. The core of the rectifier is
 324 formed by a differential drive cross-coupled (DDCC) CMOS bridge topology, which
 325 was previously found to be suitable for very low values of the input voltage and power
 326 [34–36]. The utilized circuit consists of three rectifier stages capacitively coupled to the
 327 EH coil. Each stage utilizes threshold voltage compensation for its internal switching
 328 transistors (based on the body-biasing technique) to improve the performance with the
 329 expected low RF input voltage amplitudes. The use of multiple stages was necessary
 330 to increase the total output DC voltage to a satisfactory value, at the cost of somewhat
 331 decreased overall efficiency.

Figure 8. Microphotograph of the fabricated WPT chip. The V_{DC} represents the $V_{OUT_{DC}}$ from Figure 1, i.e. the input voltage source for the CP.

332 For the purpose of experimental verification, an external transmitter circuit consist-
 333 ing of a PCB coil and a lumped impedance matching network, connected to a RF signal
 334 generator, was designed. Two transmitter coil sizes were implemented, based on sizing
 335 restrictions from [37,38]. These preliminary measurements were performed on bare die
 336 samples of the developed prototype chip, as presented in [39]. There, the measurements
 337 with the transmitter input power between 10 dBm and 20 dBm were performed, with the
 338 maximum reported DC output power of around 60 μ W and the maximum DC output
 339 voltage of more than 0.5 V, under various load conditions. These results prove the
 340 overall functionality of the implemented WPT system, as well as its suitability for use in
 341 conjunction with the developed DC-DC converter described in the previous section.

342 4. Measurement and achieved results

343 In this section, the results obtained by measurement of the prototyped chips are
 344 presented and discussed, where three branches configuration have been chosen for
 345 implementation as described in Section 2.1 in more details. The selected configuration
 346 is capable to exploit the common power availability in 10 – 100 μ W range of different
 347 energy harvester types used for IoT applications without significant form-factor violation,
 348 where the thermoelectric, bio-fuel cell or RF-based harvesters could be good candidates
 349 for utilization [1]. In order to better show the features of the proposed self-powered CP
 350 system, the measurements were done without and with RF energy harvester. For this
 351 purpose, the printed circuit test board was designed and fabricated. The measurement
 352 setup consists of the Device Under Test (DUT) with all its physical peripheries and
 353 additional circuitry as well as the instrumental equipment where the input capacitor
 354 and the output capacitor placed directly on the test board has a value of 35 μ F and
 355 69 μ F, respectively. The flying capacitors belonging to the CP have the capacitance value
 356 of 330 nF and passives corresponding to voltage divider of type 2 consist of 2x600 k Ω
 357 resistors in series with 8.5 pF capacitor at center node DIV_{EXT} .

358 4.1. Self-powered CP system

359 In Fig. 9a, one can observe the dependence of the efficiency (η) and the output
 360 voltage ($V_{CP_{OUT,avg}}$) of self-powered CP system on the output load current ($I_{LOAD,avg}$) for
 361 different external clock frequencies ($xCLK_{EXT}$) and the input voltage value $V_{OUT_{DC}}$ of
 362 180 mV (the minimum value needed to start-up the self-powered CP system). It can
 363 be observed that the maximum efficiency can be obtained for a low clock frequency
 364 and for the maximum current at the CP output. For these conditions, the efficiency of
 365 about 42 % can be achieved. However, the output voltage deviates by about 3.75 % from

366 the required value (400 mV). For higher clock frequencies, the CP system has a higher
 367 power consumption and therefore, the overall efficiency is degraded. The optimum
 368 clock frequency is about 50 kHz, where the efficiency and the output load current of
 369 43% and 23 μA were achieved, respectively. As can be observed from Fig. 9b, if the
 370 input voltage is increased to the value of 300 mV, the output current over 100 μA can be
 371 reached. In such a case, the efficiency of the self-powered CP system is less dependent
 372 on the clock frequency. It is also important to mention that the deviation of the output
 373 voltage of the CP system is mainly caused by the on-chip voltage divider because its
 374 voltage ratio depends on the clock frequency as already discussed in Section 2.3.

Figure 9. η and $V_{CP,OUT}$ vs. I_{LOAD} for different clock frequencies ('avg' in graphs stands for average value). (a) For the $V_{DC,IN}$ of 180 mV. (b) For the $V_{DC,IN}$ of 300 mV.

375 The stand-by and non-stand-by power consumptions of CP system is shown in
 376 Fig. 10, where the total power consumption was divided into contribution of individual
 377 sub-blocks of the overall CP system. Naturally, the biggest part of power consumption
 378 in the non-standby mode is given by CP Core and Driver cores which directly drives the
 379 bulky flying capacitors across charge transfer switches and boosted inverter respectively.
 380 Other sub-blocks consume less than μW of total power consumption. In the standby
 381 mode all parts have a power consumption in order of hundreds nW while the biggest
 382 part of contributors to standby power is given by comparator used in the feedback
 383 control loop across its permanent current-bias and leakage current through bulk diodes
 384 (drawback of bulk-driven design technique).

Figure 10. Distribution of power consumption across individual subsystems ($V_{DC,IN} = 200$ mV, $R_{LOAD} = 476$ k Ω , $xCLK_{EXT} = 50$ kHz). (a) Standby mode. (b) Non-standby mode (switching mode).

385 In order to investigate the possible influence on the CP system efficiency as well as
 386 for comparison of features and properties of the developed system, different types of
 387 voltage dividers were used in the measurements: a) on-chip capacitor-based voltage
 388 divider, and b) off-chip resistive voltage divider, marked as *type 1* and *type 2* (Fig. 1),
 389 respectively.

Figure 11. Comparison of different voltage dividers ('avg' in graphs stands for average value). (a) The η and $V_{CP,OUT}$ vs. I_{LOAD} for $V_{DC,IN}$ of 200 mV (b) The $V_{CP,OUT}$ vs. $V_{OUT,DC}$ for the I_{LOAD} of 10 μA .

390 As can be observed from Fig. 11a, the off-chip resistive voltage divider (marked as
 391 type 2) can help to stabilize the undesired output voltage deviation caused by different
 392 clock frequency. One can also notice that the output voltage ripple is relatively constant
 393 over the clock frequency. The efficiency of the self-powered CP system is not influenced
 394 by type of the voltage divider used. However, the maximum load current and efficiency
 395 reach slightly higher values in the case of using the capacitor-based voltage divider
 396 (marked as *type 1* in Fig. 11a).

397 Dependence of the output voltage on the input voltage is depicted in Fig. 11b, where
 398 one can see that the output voltage is independent of the clock frequency in the case of
 399 the resistive voltage divider. Additionally, the load regulation (LNR) in the worst case
 400 is 68 ppm/mV. Therefore, in order to obtain better output voltage regulation, it would
 401 be proper to use the resistive voltage divider. From the efficiency and the output load
 402 current points of view, the performed analysis show better performance in the case of
 403 using the capacitor-based voltage divider. However, such a divider should be carefully
 404 optimized for the selected clock frequency and parasitics effects to obtain desired output
 405 voltage regulation.

406 4.2. Self-powered CP system with the RF harvester

407 The results presented in the previous section were obtained with an independent
 408 voltage source used at the CP input node OUT_{DC} (see Fig. 1). In this section, we present
 409 measurement results of RF-EH system as the input voltage source for the self-powered
 410 CP system is generated directly from WPT unit. The developed RF-EH was described
 411 in Section 3. The overall system was measured for different input power P_{IN} of the
 412 external antenna and two distances between the external antenna and the implemented
 413 OCA (a part of the RF-EH).

Figure 12. Individual output voltages $V_{OUT_{DC}}$ and $V_{CP_{OUT}}$ vs. I_{LOAD} for different input powers ('avg' in graphs stands for average value). The CLK_{EXT} is set to 50 kHz and voltage divider of type 2 has been used.

414 Fig. 12 shows the dependence of the CP output voltage (and the output voltage
 415 from the on-chip RF rectifier) on the load current at the output of CP system. Presented
 416 measurement results are obtained for distance of 3 mm and 6 mm between external
 417 antenna and on-chip one for different values of the input power. The average output
 418 voltage from the rectifier is shown on the left y-axis ($V_{OUT_{DC},avg}$), while the regulated
 419 output voltage from the self-powered CP system is introduced on the right y-axis
 420 ($V_{CP_{OUT},avg}$) of the graph shown in Fig. 12. If the distance between antennas is increased
 421 twice, the input power has to be increased by 5 dBm in order to obtain the same voltage
 422 level at the RF rectifier output. The minimum input power needed for a reliable start-
 423 up of the self-powered CP system with the minimum load current (4 μ A) is 12 dBm
 424 and 16 dBm for 3 mm and 6 mm distance between the external and on-chip antennas,
 425 respectively. The regulated output voltage from the self-powered CP system was set to
 426 0.4 V, and we can observe from Fig. 12 that the system can reliably regulate the output
 427 voltage to the required value with the accuracy of $\pm 1.25\%$. Naturally, with higher input
 428 power, one can achieve a higher value of the output load current. Regarding to the CP
 429 system itself, the efficiency was not influenced. On the other hand, the efficiency of
 430 the overall CP system including the RF energy harvester will be significantly less than
 431 1%. Such a low efficiency is primarily associated with the quality factor of the on-chip
 432 inductor and with the effective chip area besides additional degrading effects (described
 433 in [31]).

434 5. Discussion and Conclusion

435 From the performed analysis, it has been shown that the proposed concept of RF-EH
 436 application using the CP-based DC-DC as a PMU can achieve promising performance
 437 even though designed in a standard pure CMOS technology. In order to highlight the
 438 important features of the proposed wireless power transfer concept, the developed
 439 CP-based DC-DC converter was compared to other state of the art works (Table 1),
 440 where the results obtained from measurement under typical conditions are presented.
 441 From Table 1, one can observe that the developed DC-DC converter is able to work
 442 with the similar input voltage values as reported in other works, except for designs
 443 presented in [40–43] and [44]. On the other hand, in our work, the converter was
 444 designed for ultra-low voltage ICs and therefore, the output voltage is lower than 1 V.
 445 The maximum peak current of 38 μ A was achieved for the input voltage of 0.2 V. If
 446 the input voltage is increased, the output current more than 100 μ A can be reached.
 447 The power conversion efficiency of the proposed converter is better than reported in
 448 the state of the art works except of [40,41,45]. However, the converters presented in
 449 [40,41] are designed for higher values of the output voltage. Finally, it is important to
 450 underline that the proposed topology achieves the best efficiency compared to the works

451 without any MPPT algorithm [44,46–49]. Therefore, one can assume that the overall
452 efficiency of the designed converter might be improved using a proper MPPT algorithm.
453 Additionally, many converters are unregulated and the power consumption of auxiliary
454 circuits forming the feedback loop are not considered in these cases. Moreover, in
455 the proposed design, the power throughput is extended to cover a broader range of
456 applications. On the other hand, our solution needs bulky external components, and
457 currently, it is not optimized for full integration.

458 The presented results, proved by measurement of prototyped chips, demonstrate
459 suitability of the proposed DC-DC converter for application in low-power and low-
460 voltage integrated systems. Additionally, it was shown that the developed converter
461 can be conveniently used in the on-chip RF-based energy harvester as a wireless power
462 transfer system. This application concept was verified by measurements, and we do
463 believe that its implementation in a standard pure CMOS technology makes the per-
464 formed research even more valuable. Finally, it is important to note that various energy
465 harvesters can be used as the input source for the proposed charge pump system. Al-
466 though, in our case, the RF harvester was used, there is no limitation for using a different
467 input energy source with an appropriate voltage range. The only strict requirement is
468 the minimum input voltage that must be about 200 mV to ensure proper functionality
469 of all blocks in the proposed CP system. Since the proposed CP system was designed
470 using BD technique, the maximum input voltage is limited to the value of 300 mV.
471 On the other hand, we have to underline that the proposed CP system was designed
472 for low-power and low-voltage applications. Therefore, using the energy harvesters
473 generating relatively higher voltages at the output is rather limited or requires additional
474 circuitry to reduce the output voltage to the appropriate level.

Table 1: Comparison of achieved results to other state-of-the-art works.

	This work	[46]	[47]	[40]	[41]	[42]	[43]	[48]	[44]	[45]	[49]
Year	2021	2018	2020	2019	2017	2017	2016	2012	2015	2020	2020
Process node [nm]	130	65	7	65	180	130	180	65	180	65	28
Area [$\cdot 10^3 \mu\text{m}^2$]	543	32	-	470	552	835	1000	783	48	1400	11.6
V_{IN} [V]	0.18-0.3	0.1-0.3	0.15	>0.55	0.5-1.8	0.25-1	0.45-3	0.12-0.16	0.5-1	0.25-1	0.04-0.1
V_{OUT} [V]	0.4-0.6	1.2 ¹⁾	0.63	1.8-2.5	1.8	1	3.3	0.77-1.32	1.8	0.9-1.5	-
V_{OUT} ripple [mV]	27.9	0.1-4	20	18	76	80	-	-	-	-	-
Peak I_{OUT} [μA]	38 ¹⁾	5 ¹⁾	1	35	19.5	500	15	<12	<7	-	-
P_{OUT} [μW]	15.2 ¹⁾	6 ¹⁾	0.68	35-70	<35.1	<500	<50	<10	10.8 ²⁾	1-100	2 ⁴⁾
Peak η [%]	43 ³⁾	45 ³⁾	31.76 ³⁾	70.8	60-72	43 ³⁾	81	40 ³⁾	52 ³⁾	>80 ⁵⁾	38.9 ³⁾
F_{SW} [MHz]	0.05 (extern)	15.2	4	1	0.1	<4.25	-	<20	-	0.1-2	1
Topology	BD cross-coupled	Cross-coupled	-	Series-parallel	-	Dickson	-	-	-	Boost+Buck SCPC	Hybrid
Number of stages	Multi-branch (3 per branch)	3	32	2	2	6	-	10	3	-	2
MPPT/Regulation	N/Y	N/N	N/Y	Y/Y	2D/Y	3D/Y	2D/Y	N/N	N/Y	2D/Y	N/N
FOM_{START-UP} ⁶⁾	0.0952 ⁷⁾	0.8512	0.2372	-	-	0.0172	0.1248 ⁸⁾	-	-	-	0.0648 ⁹⁾

1) @ V_{IN} = 0.2 V2) @ V_{IN} = 0.7 V3) @ P_{OUT} listed4) @ V_{IN} = 0.1 V,5) @ V_{IN} = 0.3 V, P_{OUT} = 5.5 μW 6) $FOM_{START-UP} = \frac{C_{LOAD}}{C_{FLY}} \frac{T_{SW}}{I_{START-UP}} \frac{\Delta V_{OUT}}{V_{IN}}$ where M represent voltage conversion ratio7) @ R_{LOAD} = 476 k Ω , V_{IN} = 200 mV, ΔV_{OUT} = 230 mV (170 mV \rightarrow 400 mV), where 170 mV is minimum start-up voltage restricted by comparator supply voltage requirement8) @ V_{IN} = 2.1 V

9) Only open circuit time response is considered

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